

P43 | Preventing respiratory viral infections in calves during prenatal and early neonatal periods

A Poryvaeva; E Pechura; I Shkuratova

"Ural Federal Agrarian Scientific Research Centre, Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences", Yekaterinburg, Russian Federation

The state of post-vaccination immunity to infectious pathogens in the dam during gestation is the decisive factor in the formation of antiviral protection of newborns in the early postnatal period. Objective: to study the dynamics of colostral immunity against respiratory viral infections (ARVI) in calves born from vaccinated cows. The immunity in dams vaccinated during pregnancy ($n = 132$) with an inactivated Russia-produced multivalent vaccine against ARVI pathogens was determined by titers of specific antibodies in blood serums. The titer of antibodies to Bovine herpesvirus 1 (BoHV-1) was 5.82 ± 0.23 log; to bovine parainfluenza virus type 3 (BPIV3)– 9.02 ± 0.34 log, to bovine viral diarrhoea virus (BVDV)– 6.76 ± 0.28 log. The serum titres in calves ($n = 132$) given colostrum from these dams, were determined between day 1 and 3 of life: titres to BoHV-1 was 4.58 ± 0.16 log; BPIV3– 7.64 ± 0.28 log; to BVDV – 5.28 ± 0.16 log. Up to 10 days there were no changes in titres. By day 20, a decrease was registered in the antibody titers to BoHV-1 (2.54 ± 0.22 log; BPIV3 – up to 4.84 ± 0.31 log; BVDV – up to 2.84 ± 0.24 log). These titres are regarded as minimum protective levels. By day 30, the antibody titres in 87.5% of calves to ARVI pathogens were further decreased (BoHV-1 – 1.8 ± 0.14 log; BPIV3 – 3.2 ± 0.17 log; to BVDV – 2.19 ± 0.19 log.) None of the calves showed clinical symptoms during the study period. These data suggest that regular vaccination in the third semester of the pregnancy of cows provides humoral immunity against AVRI in the calves in the neonatal period. If this immunity is protective against AVRI must be tested in a proper challenge study.

P44 | Effect of EGF on viability of cryopreserved beef bull semen

L Vincenti¹; A Reda Elkhawagah²; A Ricci¹; T Nervo¹; D Gallo³

¹DPT Veterinary Science, Grugliasco, Italy; ²Theriogenology Department, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Benha University, Benha, Egypt; ³Laboratory of Endocrinology, Diabetology and Metabolism, Division of Endocrinology Diabetology and Metabolism, Department of Medical Sciences, University of Torino, Torino, Italy

Different concentration of Epidermal Growth Factor (EGF): 0 (control) 50, 100, 200 and 400 ng/ml, before cryopreservation was used to improve the vitality of diluted bull semen. Semen was collected weekly for 8 weeks from 4 Piedmontese beef bulls, pooled and extended with Bullxcell extender. After dilution, semen was cooled, equilibrated and finally frozen in the liquid nitrogen. After thawing at 37°C for 40 s, semen was assessed for sperm motility and velocity parameters with CASA after 0, 1, 2, 3 and 4 h of incubation at 37°C; in addition to sperm vitality, acrosome, plasma membrane and DNA integrities,

apoptosis, mitochondrial membrane potential, mucus penetration distance and superoxide dismutase activity, were performed. The data were analyzed as mean \pm SEM with ANOVA. Duncan test was used for multiple comparisons and Pearson correlations for different parameters correlations. P value was set at < 0.05 to define statistical significance. EGF significantly ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$) improved the total sperm motility after 0, 1,3 and 4 h incubation mainly with the concentrations 100 and 200 ng/ml. The progressive motility after 1 and 2 h and the rapid motility after 1, 2 and 3 h of incubation ($p < 0.01$) mainly with the concentration 200 ng/ml were improved. The EGF significantly ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.05$) improves the different velocity parameters after the different incubation periods mainly with the concentrations 100, 200 and 400 ng/ml. EGF significantly improved the sperm vitality ($p < 0.01$) and decreased sperm apoptosis ($p < 0.05$) with the concentrations 100, 200 and 400 ng/ml without affecting acrosome, plasma membrane and DNA integrities. In conclusions, incorporation of EGF especially at concentrations 100 and 200 ng/ml could improve the vitality parameters of cryopreserved bull semen.

P45 | Results of vaginal samples in cows in the post partum period

S Makavchik; A Sukhinin; Y Danko; V Kuzmin; I Belkina

St. Petersburg state academy of veterinary medicine, Saint-Petersburg, Russian Federation

One of the main reasons for the reduction of fertility in farms are infectious diseases of cattle, leading to disturbances in the reproductive system of cows, resulting in pregnancy problems, fetal death, abortion at any time during pregnancy and stillbirth. The material for this study was 110 vaginal swabs and scrapings of cows in the post partum period. We used microscopic methods as well as cultivation on nutrient media. Identification was performed using test systems API 20E, BioMerieux, France, as well as using MALDI Biotyper, Helena Biosciences Europe, United Kingdom. Bacteriological analysis from vaginal samples revealed a wide range of microorganisms: E. coli in 12.9% of cases, K. pneumoniae (8.3%), Proteus sp. (8%), C. albicans (6%), P. aeruginosa (6%), Staphylococcus sp. (4%), Streptococcus sp. (3%), Bacillus sp. (3.2%), Serratia sp. (1.4%), Corynebacterium sp. (4.2%). Polymerase chain reaction in microchip format for the diagnosis and monitoring of pathogens of urogenital infections in cattle was also performed from clinical samples. For amplification, RT-PCR cyclor AriaDNA with a microchip with lyophilized reagents developed by IC Lumex was used. In the samples, the microorganisms Mycoplasma and Ureaplasma were simultaneously identified in 55% of cases; and Mycoplasma, Ureaplasma and Chlamydia in 5%. Microbes in an ascending direction might cause the development of inflammation in the vagina, cervix, and then also in the uterus if immune protection is decreased. The period of risk of infection with microorganisms is during the passage through the birth canal at parturition. Laboratory diagnostics allow timely treatment and prevention of diseases by management optimising.